

Supplementary Figure 1: AMPK- phosphorylating activity of nutraceuticals - K562 cells were treated for 24 hrs with different concentration of the indicated compounds. Equal amount of protein from each condition was separated on SDS PAGE (12% gel) and protein expression levels were investigated through western blot analysis using antibody against phosphorylated and total AMPK. Vinculin has been used as internal control. Upper vinculin is referred to pAMPK, lower vinculin is referred to AMPK.

Supplementary Figure 2: SEC elution profile of the AMPK, ACLY and LKB1 in K562 cells under control (left panel) and HCA treatment (right panel). Protein lysate from HCA treated and control K562 cell was analysed by size-exclusion chromatography to examine if they are part of the same complex. ACLY peaks at the fraction 4 and 5 (corresponding to C7 and C8 of the Superose 6 column) and co-eluted with AMPK which peaks at the fraction 8 (C11 of the Superose 6 column) (Figure 2C, left panel). This suggest that AMPK and ACLY are a part of complex. Although HCA treated samples ACLY showed more broader peak ranging from fraction 3 to 6 (C6 to C9 of the Superose 6 column) and still it seems to co-eluted with AMPK which peaks at fraction 8 and 9 (C12-D12 of the Superose 6 column) (Figure 2C, right panel).

Supplementary Figure 3. HCA induces neither apoptosis nor autophagy in K562 cells. K562 cells were treated with different concentrations of HCA for 24 and 48 hrs, as indicated. (A) activation of autophagy was analyzed by immunoblotting for LC3. (B) activation of apoptosis was analyzed by immunoblotting for cleaved caspase 3. (C). The annexin V/PI staining was performed and analyzed by FACS.